

CHARACTERIZATION OF FIGURES IN SHUKUR XOLMIRZAYEV’S STORIES

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Abstract: This article analyzes the stories of Shukur Xolmirzayev, focusing on the characterization of the figures depicted therein. The author examines the social status, lifestyle, and character of city dwellers, nomads, villagers, and their portrayal in society.

Key words: Character, figure, people, story, style, author, writer, city, desert, village.

Shukur Xolmirzayev has played a significant role in the development of Uzbek literature in the 20th century, thanks to his high literary talent and the extraordinary prose he has created. He holds a unique position in the spiritual development of the Uzbek people. Starting his literary career at the age of eighteen, he emerged as one of our distinguished writers, entering the literary world alongside seasoned writers. The writer’s first creative work is directly related to the genre of storytelling. When discussing any literary work, he not only analyzes the literary aspects but also encourages readers to study beyond literature itself. While his narratives express the romanticism of youth and student years in life's processes, they also capture the life of Turkestan natives residing in the village of Boysun, showcasing their struggle and changes in their spiritual world.

The writer possesses a unique style. In 1978, Professor U. Normatov noted the following regarding Shukur Xolmirzayev's distinctive literary style: “Shukur Xolmirzayev's stories captivate attention with their stylistic features, expressive methods, the atmosphere of their descriptions, and their rhythm.”¹The style mentioned by the critic is indicative of the author’s habit of succinctly describing his thoughts. Shukur Xolmirzayev is a phenomenon in 20th century national storytelling. This phenomenon, according to the concept of the “Uzbekistan National Encyclopedia,” is a philosophical concept that is associated with extraordinary

¹ Normatov U. “Our traditional ancestors.” Page 205.

events, facts, and personal experiences”² that are reinforced with perceptions of truths.

Most of the author's works feature laborers from Surkhondaryo. The address, which is also the location where these heroes typically live, is common in this work. These characters serve as symbols of the Uzbek nation and the Turkic culture, illustrating their distinctiveness. The writer does not overburden or force his work on characters. His primary focus is to show how they regard friendships, new lives, and changes, as well as how to view them as well as to understand and enjoy them.

The protagonist of the story “The Death of Shepherd” was someone who was deeply averse to harming innocent creatures. As described by the writers: “He would handle a lamb with as much care as a child holds onto its father when he dies...”³ Nowadays, issues such as preserving and conserving nature are emerging as crucial dilemmas. In Shukur Xolmirzayev's “The Death of a Shepherd,” everything in nature is portrayed with its due importance. What will happen in the end is a lesson for all of us. Students read this work and empathize with all living beings in nature. The reader learns the importance of not being indifferent to incidents in nature. Thus, through this story, our writer reminds us that every action we take has consequences, using the shepherd's fate as an example. In today's world, young people read this work and consider the kind of environment they should create within their families, how to raise their children, and realize that love and respect for their loved ones are essential, rather than using ideas such as “sin” and “bloodshed” brought down by their ancestors, and most importantly, that each of the residents living in our world. In the stories of the writer, the characters depicted are primarily drawn from real life. While it's true that all writers draw events from life, the author strives to accurately portray the internal character of their characters. This means that you can observe both positive and negative traits in a person when you look closely at them, which often leaves you amazed. People in real life possess this complexity, but we may not always recognize it and tend to hide it.

In the author's stories, the simple villagers toiling hard and spending their lives amidst the natural beauty of the countryside stand in contrast to the city dwellers consumed by work and the hustle and bustle of urban life. Each of these characters occupies a unique place, reflecting various aspects of our national identity and portraying different facets of folk culture values.

The characters in the author's stories possess distinctive personalities, and their narrative arcs complement each other, amplifying the conclusions drawn from their

² Uzbekistan National Encyclopedia

³ <https://www.ziyouz.com>

actions and interactions, as well as the insights derived from their natural surroundings. The author's works do not shy away from depicting the challenges and joys of rural life, and they also delve into deeper moral issues. The contemporary situations depicted in these stories indicate a serious negative impact on our emotional stability and independence.

Literary Sources:

1. Normatov U. “Our traditional ancestors.” Page 205.
2. Uzbekistan National Encyclopedia
3. <https://www.ziyouz.com>